

Complete Numerical Tables for the Data Repository

MAC-Layer Throughput Modeling in IEEE 802.11

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This document consolidates the complete numerical tables associated with the manuscript. It preserves the full set of frame sizes, including $L = 64$, 512, 1024, and 1500 bytes where applicable, so that the condensed boundary-case tables in the main paper can be accompanied by a complete repository record for traceability and reproducibility.

1 General reference tables

Table 1: Relationship between IEEE 802.11 amendments, technical designations, and Wi-Fi generation names.

IEEE amendment	Technical designation	Wi-Fi generation	Main identification
IEEE 802.11a	OFDM	–	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
IEEE 802.11b	HR-DSSS	–	High-Rate Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum
IEEE 802.11g	ERP-OFDM	–	Extended Rate Physical - Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
IEEE 802.11n	HT	Wi-Fi 4	High Throughput
IEEE 802.11ac	VHT	Wi-Fi 5	Very High Throughput
IEEE 802.11ax	HE	Wi-Fi 6 / Wi-Fi 6E ^a	High Efficiency
IEEE 802.11be	EHT	Wi-Fi 7	Extremely High Throughput
IEEE 802.11bt	PQC	–	Post-Quantum Cryptography amendment

^a Wi-Fi 6E denotes 802.11ax operation extended to the 6 GHz band

Table 2: Main parameters and constants assumed in the analytical models.

Parameter	Definition	Assumed value
s	IEEE 802.11 amendment considered in the model	$s \in \{a, b, g, n, ac, ax, be\}$
L	Useful MSDU payload size	$L \in \{64, 512, 1024, 1500\}$ bytes
H_{LLC}	Logical Link Control/Subnetwork Access Protocol (LLC/SNAP) encapsulation overhead	8 bytes
$H_{MAC}^{(a/b/g)}$	MAC header assumed for legacy IEEE 802.11a/b/g frames	30 bytes
$H_{MAC}^{(n+)}$	MAC header assumed for IEEE 802.11n/ac/ax/be aggregated frames	36 bytes
H_{FCS}	Frame Check Sequence (FCS) overhead	4 bytes
H_{DELIM}	MPDU delimiter overhead in A-MPDU aggregation	4 bytes
$B_{SERVICE}$	SERVICE field size	16 bits
B_{TAIL}	TAIL field size	6 bits
B_{ST}	SERVICE plus TAIL contribution	22 bits
$AIFSN(AC_BE)$	Arbitration Interframe Space Number (AIFSN) for the Best Effort access category (AC_BE)	3
$AIFS$	Arbitration interframe space (AIFS) for IEEE 802.11a/g/n/ac/ax/be under the Best Effort access category	43 μs
$SlotTime$	Duration of one contention slot	20 μs for IEEE 802.11b; 9 μs for IEEE 802.11a/g/n/ac/ax/be
CW_{min}, CW_{max}	Minimum and maximum contention-window values	31 and 1023 for IEEE 802.11b; 15 and 1023 for IEEE 802.11a/g/n/ac/ax/be
$\mathbb{E}[BO]$	Mean initial backoff timer duration	310 μs for IEEE 802.11b; 67.5 μs for IEEE 802.11a/g/n/ac/ax/be
$DIFS^{(11b)}$	Distributed interframe space (DIFS) for IEEE 802.11b	50 μs
$SIFS$	Short interframe space (SIFS)	10 μs for IEEE 802.11b; 16 μs for IEEE 802.11a/g/n/ac/ax/be
$T_{sym}^{(a/g)}$	Legacy Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing (OFDM) symbol duration	4 μs
$T_{sym}(s)$	OFDM symbol duration for aggregated amendments	3.6 μs for IEEE 802.11n/ac; 13.6 μs for IEEE 802.11ax/be
$T_{PLCP,pre}^{(11b)}$	IEEE 802.11b Physical Layer Convergence Procedure (PLCP) preamble duration	72 μs
$T_{PLCP,hdr}^{(11b)}$	IEEE 802.11b PLCP header duration	24 μs
$T_{preamble}^{(a/g)}$	Legacy OFDM preamble duration	20 μs
$T_{preamble}(s)$	The PHY preamble duration assumed for A-MPDU data transmission	24 μs for IEEE 802.11n; 40 μs for IEEE 802.11ac; 40 μs for IEEE 802.11ax; 44 μs for IEEE 802.11be
$R_{ACK}^{(11b)}$	Acknowledgment (ACK) transmission rate assumed for IEEE 802.11b	2 Mbps
R_{ctrl}	Legacy OFDM control-frame rate assumed for ACK/Block ACK timing, assuming basic service set (BSS) BasicRateSet in 54 Mbps	54 Mbps
T_{ACK}	ACK transmission time	152 μs for IEEE 802.11b; 28 μs for IEEE 802.11a/g
H_{BACK}	Compressed Block ACK size	32 bytes
T_{BACK}	Compressed Block ACK transmission time	28 μs
$M_{frame}(s)$	Normative A-MPDU size limit	65,535 bytes for IEEE 802.11n; 1,048,575 bytes for IEEE 802.11ac; 6,500,631 bytes for IEEE 802.11ax; 15,523,198 bytes for IEEE 802.11be
$X_{max}(s)$	Maximum number of MPDUs per A-MPDU	64 for IEEE 802.11n/ac; 256 for IEEE 802.11ax; 512 for IEEE 802.11be
$T_{cap}(s)$	Physical Layer Protocol Data Unit (PPDU) temporal limit applied to the PHY transmission interval	10,000 μs for IEEE 802.11n High Throughput (HT) greenfield; 5,484 μs for IEEE 802.11ac/ax/be

2 Complete measured throughput and performance tables

Table 3: Throughput comparison and performance indicators — 802.11b.

Frame	Data rate	Throughput			Performance indicators			
		Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Measured throughput (Th_m)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_m$	CPU	Latency	Jitter	Frame rate ^a
1500 bytes	11 Mbps	6.9 Mbps	6.7 Mbps	0.2 Mbps	3 %	374 ms	14 ms	560 pps
1024 bytes	11 Mbps	5.9 Mbps	5.3 Mbps	0.6 Mbps	4 %	420 ms	10 ms	715 pps
512 bytes	11 Mbps	4.0 Mbps	4.1 Mbps	-0.1 Mbps	4 %	587 ms	16 ms	1000 pps
64 bytes	11 Mbps	0.7 Mbps	0.8 Mbps	-0.1 Mbps	5 %	390 ms	17 ms	1500 pps

^a pps stands for frames per second

Table 4: Throughput comparison and performance indicators — 802.11g.

Frame	Data rate	Throughput			BER parameters		Performance indicators	
		Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Measured throughput (Th_m)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_m$	Adjusted BER	Effective success prob.	CPU	Latency / Jitter / Frame rate
1500 bytes	54 Mbps	29.5 Mbps	26.3 Mbps	+3.2 Mbps	9.3×10^{-6}	89.2%	8 %	99 ms / 13 ms / 2200 pps
1024 bytes	54 Mbps	24.5 Mbps	21.7 Mbps	+2.8 Mbps	1.4×10^{-5}	88.6%	8 %	117 ms / 12 ms / 2600 pps
512 bytes	54 Mbps	15.8 Mbps	13.9 Mbps	+1.9 Mbps	2.9×10^{-5}	88.0%	9 %	185 ms / 13 ms / 3600 pps
64 bytes	54 Mbps	2.7 Mbps	2.3 Mbps	+0.4 Mbps	1.9×10^{-4}	85.2%	10 %	133 ms / 14 ms / 4600 pps

Table 5: Throughput comparison and performance indicators — 802.11a.

Frame	Data rate	Throughput			BER parameters		Performance indicators	
		Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Measured throughput (Th_m)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_m$	Adjusted BER	Effective success prob.	CPU	Latency / Jitter / Frame rate
1500 bytes	54 Mbps	29.5 Mbps	26.4 Mbps	+3.1 Mbps	9.0×10^{-6}	89.5%	10 %	97 ms / 15 ms / 2100 pps
1024 bytes	54 Mbps	24.5 Mbps	22.0 Mbps	+2.5 Mbps	1.3×10^{-5}	89.8%	10 %	113 ms / 17 ms / 2700 pps
512 bytes	54 Mbps	15.8 Mbps	15.1 Mbps	+0.7 Mbps	1.0×10^{-5}	95.6%	12 %	160 ms / 17 ms / 3700 pps
64 bytes	54 Mbps	2.7 Mbps	1.6 Mbps	+1.1 Mbps	6.1×10^{-4}	59.3%	12 %	190 ms / 15 ms / 3200 pps

Table 6: Throughput comparison and performance indicators — IEEE 802.11n/ac, A-MPDU at 5 GHz / 20 MHz.

Standard	Frame	Data rate	Throughput			BER parameters		Performance indicators	
			Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Measured throughput (Th_m)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_m$	Adjusted BER	Effective success prob.	CPU	Latency / Jitter / Frame rate
802.11n	1500 bytes	72.2 Mbps	68.1 Mbps	66.1 Mbps	+2.0 Mbps	2.37×10^{-6}	97.1%	20 %	47.5 ms / 12 ms / 5500 pps
802.11ac	1500 bytes	86.7 Mbps	80.9 Mbps	78.2 Mbps	+2.7 Mbps	2.72×10^{-6}	96.7%	25 %	41.0 ms / 13 ms / 6600 pps
802.11n	1024 bytes	72.2 Mbps	67.0 Mbps	65.4 Mbps	+1.6 Mbps	2.82×10^{-6}	97.6%	29 %	46.0 ms / 13 ms / 7900 pps
802.11ac	1024 bytes	86.7 Mbps	79.6 Mbps	77.1 Mbps	+2.5 Mbps	3.68×10^{-6}	96.9%	30 %	39.4 ms / 12 ms / 9400 pps
802.11n	512 bytes	72.2 Mbps	62.7 Mbps	59.6 Mbps	+3.1 Mbps	1.12×10^{-5}	95.1%	47 %	45.0 ms / 13 ms / 14500 pps
802.11ac	512 bytes	86.7 Mbps	74.3 Mbps	70.0 Mbps	+4.3 Mbps	1.32×10^{-5}	94.2%	50 %	38.0 ms / 13 ms / 17000 pps
802.11n	64 bytes	72.2 Mbps	32.7 Mbps	14.1 Mbps	+18.6 Mbps	9.05×10^{-4}	43.2%	75 %	26.3 ms / 14 ms / 27700 pps
802.11ac	64 bytes	86.7 Mbps	37.1 Mbps	16.1 Mbps	+21.0 Mbps	9.01×10^{-4}	43.3%	72 %	23.4 ms / 13 ms / 31700 pps

Table 7: Throughput comparison and performance indicators — 802.11n/ac, A-MPDU at 5 GHz / 40 MHz.

Standard	Frame	Data rate	Throughput			BER parameters		Performance indicators	
			Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Measured throughput (Th_m)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_m$	Adjusted BER	Effective success prob.	CPU	Latency / Jitter / Frame rate
802.11n	1500 bytes	150 Mbps	137.9 Mbps	133.4 Mbps	+4.5 Mbps	2.64×10^{-6}	96.8%	40%	27.0 ms / 10 ms / 11100 pps
802.11ac	1500 bytes	200 Mbps	184.2 Mbps	170.0 Mbps	+14.2 Mbps	6.47×10^{-6}	92.3%	40%	22.0 ms / 12 ms / 14200 pps
802.11n	1024 bytes	150 Mbps	135.6 Mbps	127.4 Mbps	+8.2 Mbps	7.28×10^{-6}	93.9%	46%	25.0 ms / 9 ms / 15550 pps
802.11ac	1024 bytes	200 Mbps	177.6 Mbps	156.0 Mbps	+21.6 Mbps	1.51×10^{-5}	87.8%	57%	21.0 ms / 13 ms / 19000 pps
802.11n	512 bytes	150 Mbps	124.6 Mbps	111.4 Mbps	+13.2 Mbps	2.48×10^{-5}	89.4%	80%	25.0 ms / 13 ms / 27300 pps
802.11ac	512 bytes	200 Mbps	159.7 Mbps	133.0 Mbps	+26.7 Mbps	4.05×10^{-5}	83.3%	80%	22.0 ms / 14 ms / 32000 pps
802.11n	64 bytes	150 Mbps	56.7 Mbps	22.6 Mbps	+34.1 Mbps	9.90×10^{-4}	39.9%	80%	18.3 ms / 13 ms / 44200 pps
802.11ac	64 bytes	200 Mbps	66.4 Mbps	24.6 Mbps	+41.8 Mbps	1.07×10^{-3}	37.0%	75%	17.2 ms / 12 ms / 48000 pps

Table 8: Throughput comparison and performance indicators — 802.11n, A-MPDU at 2.4 GHz / 20 MHz.

Frame	Data rate	Throughput			BER parameters		Performance indicators	
		Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Measured throughput (Th_m)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_m$	Adjusted BER	Effective success prob.	CPU	Latency / Jitter / Frame rate
1500 bytes	72.2 Mbps	68.1 Mbps	60.3 Mbps	+7.8 Mbps	9.80×10^{-6}	88.5%	10%	52 ms / 21 ms / 5000 pps
1024 bytes	72.2 Mbps	67.0 Mbps	59.0 Mbps	+8.0 Mbps	1.48×10^{-5}	88.1%	15%	50 ms / 25 ms / 7250 pps
512 bytes	72.2 Mbps	62.7 Mbps	55.0 Mbps	+7.7 Mbps	2.90×10^{-5}	87.7%	30%	49 ms / 15 ms / 13600 pps
64 bytes	72.2 Mbps	32.7 Mbps	13.0 Mbps	+19.7 Mbps	9.93×10^{-4}	39.8%	60%	28 ms / 14 ms / 25600 pps

Table 9: Throughput comparison and performance indicators — 802.11n, A-MPDU at 2.4 GHz / 40 MHz.

Frame	Data rate	Throughput			BER parameters		Performance indicators	
		Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Measured throughput (Th_m)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_m$	Adjusted BER	Effective success prob.	CPU	Latency / Jitter / Frame rate
1500 bytes	150 Mbps	137.9 Mbps	123.0 Mbps	+14.9 Mbps	9.18×10^{-6}	89.2%	20%	28 ms / 16 ms / 10200 pps
1024 bytes	150 Mbps	135.6 Mbps	116.0 Mbps	+19.6 Mbps	1.82×10^{-5}	85.5%	34%	27 ms / 14 ms / 14400 pps
512 bytes	150 Mbps	124.6 Mbps	104.5 Mbps	+20.1 Mbps	3.89×10^{-5}	83.9%	60%	26.5 ms / 10 ms / 25600 pps
64 bytes	150 Mbps	56.7 Mbps	21.5 Mbps	+35.2 Mbps	1.04×10^{-3}	37.9%	70%	19 ms / 11 ms / 42000 pps

3 Complete effective-BER calibration and inference tables

Table 10: Empirical P_b ratio for IEEE 802.11n/ac at 5 GHz / 20 and 40 MHz.

B_{channel}	Frame L	$P_b^{(n)}$	$P_b^{(ac)}$	$k_{ac/n}(L)$
20 MHz	1500 bytes	2.37×10^{-6}	2.72×10^{-6}	1.15
20 MHz	1024 bytes	2.82×10^{-6}	3.68×10^{-6}	1.30
20 MHz	512 bytes	1.12×10^{-5}	1.32×10^{-5}	1.18
20 MHz	64 bytes	9.05×10^{-4}	9.01×10^{-4}	1.00
Geometric mean $\bar{k}_{ac/n}$ for 20 MHz				1.15
40 MHz	1500 bytes	2.64×10^{-6}	6.47×10^{-6}	2.45
40 MHz	1024 bytes	7.28×10^{-6}	1.51×10^{-5}	2.07
40 MHz	512 bytes	2.48×10^{-5}	4.05×10^{-5}	1.63
40 MHz	64 bytes	9.90×10^{-4}	1.07×10^{-3}	1.08
Geometric mean $\bar{k}_{ac/n}$ for 40 MHz				1.73

Table 11: Definition of the parameters used to calculate $k_{\text{std}/n}$ (n/ac reference: MikroTik; ax/be reference: Aruba 730).

Band	B_{channel}	Std/MCS ^a	Data rate	$S_{\text{min}}^{(\text{std})}$	$S_{\text{min}}^{(n)}$	$\Delta_{\text{std}/n}$	a	$k_{\text{std}/n}$
2.4 GHz	20 MHz	ax MCS11	143.4 Mbps	-62 dBm	-76 dBm	14 dB	0.01214	1.479
2.4 GHz	20 MHz	be MCS13	172.1 Mbps	-58 dBm	-76 dBm	18 dB	0.01214	1.654
2.4 GHz	40 MHz	ax MCS11	286.8 Mbps	-60 dBm	-73 dBm	13 dB	0.02976	2.437
2.4 GHz	40 MHz	be MCS13	344.1 Mbps	-55 dBm	-73 dBm	18 dB	0.02976	3.432
5 GHz	20 MHz	ax MCS11	143.4 Mbps	-61 dBm	-77 dBm	16 dB	0.01214	1.564
5 GHz	20 MHz	be MCS13	172.1 Mbps	-56 dBm	-77 dBm	21 dB	0.01214	1.799
5 GHz	40 MHz	ax MCS11	286.8 Mbps	-59 dBm	-74 dBm	15 dB	0.02976	2.795
5 GHz	40 MHz	be MCS13	344.1 Mbps	-53 dBm	-74 dBm	21 dB	0.02976	4.216

^a MCS stands for Modulation and Coding Scheme

Table 12: Inferred BER (P_b) for the IEEE 802.11ax/be amendments.

Band	B_{channel}	Data rate	Frame	$P_b^{(ax)}$	$P_b^{(be)}$
2.4 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	1500 bytes	1.45×10^{-5}	1.62×10^{-5}
2.4 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	1024 bytes	2.19×10^{-5}	2.45×10^{-5}
2.4 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	512 bytes	4.29×10^{-5}	4.80×10^{-5}
2.4 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	64 bytes	1.47×10^{-3}	1.64×10^{-3}
2.4 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	1500 bytes	2.24×10^{-5}	3.15×10^{-5}
2.4 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	1024 bytes	4.44×10^{-5}	6.25×10^{-5}
2.4 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	512 bytes	9.48×10^{-5}	1.34×10^{-4}
2.4 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	64 bytes	2.53×10^{-3}	3.57×10^{-3}
5 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	1500 bytes	3.71×10^{-6}	4.26×10^{-6}
5 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	1024 bytes	4.41×10^{-6}	5.07×10^{-6}
5 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	512 bytes	1.75×10^{-5}	2.01×10^{-5}
5 GHz	20 MHz	ax: 143.4 Mbps be: 172.1 Mbps	64 bytes	1.42×10^{-3}	1.63×10^{-3}
5 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	1500 bytes	7.38×10^{-6}	1.11×10^{-5}
5 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	1024 bytes	2.03×10^{-5}	3.07×10^{-5}
5 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	512 bytes	6.93×10^{-5}	1.05×10^{-4}
5 GHz	40 MHz	ax: 286.8 Mbps be: 344.1 Mbps	64 bytes	2.77×10^{-3}	4.17×10^{-3}

The baseline $P_b^{(n)}$ was taken directly from Tables 8 and 9 for 2.4 GHz and from Tables 6 and 7 for 5 GHz, while $k_{\text{std}/n}$ was obtained from Table 11, assuming $\Delta_{ac/n,\text{eff}} = 8$ dB exclusively in the calibration of a for $B_{\text{channel}} = 40$ MHz.

4 Complete IEEE 802.11ax/be inferred throughput tables

Table 13: Throughput comparison — IEEE 802.11ax/be, A-MPDU at 5 GHz / 20 MHz.

Standard	Frame	Data rate	Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Inferred throughput (Th_i)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_i$	Effective success prob.
802.11ax	1500 bytes	143.4 Mbps	133.66 Mbps	127.64 Mbps	+6.02 Mbps	95.5%
802.11be	1500 bytes	172.1 Mbps	160.19 Mbps	151.94 Mbps	+8.25 Mbps	94.8%
802.11ax	1024 bytes	143.4 Mbps	131.62 Mbps	126.72 Mbps	+4.90 Mbps	96.3%
802.11be	1024 bytes	172.1 Mbps	157.74 Mbps	151.00 Mbps	+6.74 Mbps	95.7%
802.11ax	512 bytes	143.4 Mbps	125.64 Mbps	116.10 Mbps	+9.54 Mbps	92.4%
802.11be	512 bytes	172.1 Mbps	150.37 Mbps	137.33 Mbps	+13.04 Mbps	91.3%
802.11ax	64 bytes	143.4 Mbps	70.71 Mbps	18.91 Mbps	+51.80 Mbps	26.7%
802.11be	64 bytes	172.1 Mbps	88.47 Mbps	19.47 Mbps	+69.00 Mbps	22.0%

Table 14: Throughput comparison — IEEE 802.11ax/be, A-MPDU at 5 GHz / 40 MHz.

Standard	Frame	Data rate	Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Inferred throughput (Th_i)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_i$	Effective success prob.
802.11ax	1500 bytes	286.8 Mbps	267.51 Mbps	244.09 Mbps	+23.42 Mbps	91.2%
802.11be	1500 bytes	344.1 Mbps	320.39 Mbps	279.04 Mbps	+41.35 Mbps	87.1%
802.11ax	1024 bytes	286.8 Mbps	263.24 Mbps	220.95 Mbps	+42.29 Mbps	83.9%
802.11be	1024 bytes	344.1 Mbps	315.55 Mbps	242.29 Mbps	+73.26 Mbps	76.8%
802.11ax	512 bytes	286.8 Mbps	248.30 Mbps	181.62 Mbps	+66.68 Mbps	73.1%
802.11be	512 bytes	344.1 Mbps	300.74 Mbps	187.63 Mbps	+113.11 Mbps	62.4%
802.11ax	64 bytes	286.8 Mbps	127.99 Mbps	9.78 Mbps	+118.21 Mbps	7.6%
802.11be	64 bytes	344.1 Mbps	165.77 Mbps	3.42 Mbps	+162.35 Mbps	2.1%

Table 15: Throughput comparison — IEEE 802.11ax/be, A-MPDU at 2.4 GHz / 20 MHz.

Standard	Frame	Data rate	Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Inferred throughput (Th_i)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_i$	Effective success prob.
802.11ax	1500 bytes	143.4 Mbps	133.66 Mbps	111.64 Mbps	+22.02 Mbps	83.5%
802.11be	1500 bytes	172.1 Mbps	160.19 Mbps	131.01 Mbps	+29.18 Mbps	81.8%
802.11ax	1024 bytes	143.4 Mbps	131.62 Mbps	109.01 Mbps	+22.61 Mbps	82.8%
802.11be	1024 bytes	172.1 Mbps	157.74 Mbps	127.75 Mbps	+29.99 Mbps	81.0%
802.11ax	512 bytes	143.4 Mbps	125.64 Mbps	103.53 Mbps	+22.11 Mbps	82.4%
802.11be	512 bytes	172.1 Mbps	150.37 Mbps	121.09 Mbps	+29.28 Mbps	80.5%
802.11ax	64 bytes	143.4 Mbps	70.71 Mbps	18.05 Mbps	+52.66 Mbps	25.5%
802.11be	64 bytes	172.1 Mbps	88.47 Mbps	19.29 Mbps	+69.18 Mbps	21.8%

Table 16: Throughput comparison — IEEE 802.11ax/be, A-MPDU at 2.4 GHz / 40 MHz.

Standard	Frame	Data rate	Calculated throughput (Th_c)	Inferred throughput (Th_i)	$\Delta = Th_c - Th_i$	Effective success prob.
802.11ax	1500 bytes	286.8 Mbps	267.51 Mbps	202.56 Mbps	+64.95 Mbps	75.7%
802.11be	1500 bytes	344.1 Mbps	320.39 Mbps	216.68 Mbps	+103.71 Mbps	67.6%
802.11ax	1024 bytes	286.8 Mbps	263.24 Mbps	179.62 Mbps	+83.62 Mbps	68.2%
802.11be	1024 bytes	344.1 Mbps	315.55 Mbps	184.25 Mbps	+131.30 Mbps	58.4%
802.11ax	512 bytes	286.8 Mbps	248.30 Mbps	161.88 Mbps	+86.42 Mbps	65.2%
802.11be	512 bytes	344.1 Mbps	300.74 Mbps	164.28 Mbps	+136.46 Mbps	54.6%
802.11ax	64 bytes	286.8 Mbps	127.99 Mbps	12.20 Mbps	+115.79 Mbps	9.5%
802.11be	64 bytes	344.1 Mbps	165.77 Mbps	6.00 Mbps	+159.77 Mbps	3.6%

5 Monte Carlo simulation parameter table

Table 17: Monte Carlo simulation parameters for BO_{eff} (802.11b and 802.11ac).

Parameter	802.11b (DCF)	802.11ac (EDCA/A-MPDU)
Number of realizations (n_{MC})	20000	20000
Pseudo-random generator seed	1234	1234
P_b (BER)	0.0	0.0
L (bytes)	{64, 512, 1024, 1500}	
$SlotTime$ (μs)	20.0	9.0
Resumption interframe space (IFS) (μs)	$DIFS = 50.0$	$AIFS = 43.0$
CW_{min}	31	15
CW_{max}	1023	1023
Retransmission limit (#retries)	7	7
Prob. of missing acknowledgment ($p_{\text{noACK/noBA}}$)	0.10	0.10
(Block) Acknowledgment timeout (μs)	250.0	150.0
Prob. of busy medium during countdown (p_{busy})	0.05	0.05
Average busy duration (slots)	20	20
Data rate	11 Mbps	200 Mbps